

ASPECTS REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MODERN MANAGEMENT METHODS AND ADVANCED TRAINING TECHNOLOGIES IN ORDER TO MAKE THE TRAINING OF ATHLETES MORE EFFICIENT

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Abstract

Purpose: *The aim of this study was to make sports management more efficient through the use of advanced technologies, including as a case study to investigate the relationship between accelerated growth, objectified by parameters: height, weight, BMI and cardiac endurance in junior athletes (10-14 years), members of sports clubs, practitioners of sports games (football).*

Methodology/approach: *The research methodology was based on the measurement of anthropometric and biochemical parameters of a group of 124 male athletes, 10 of which were valid in 34 athletes, as some were not measured in all 10 parameters, and other athletes had vitiated the result of the measurement, all 124 athletes being underage students, aged between 6 and 12 years. The variation of these parameters was studied with the help of mathematical methods that led to the objective identification of the physical potential by the sports technician, coach and even by the beneficiary or beneficiaries of the analysis (athlete or athletes), physical potential that can be minimum, maximum, constancy, or its trend: in progression or regression.*

Findings: *The results highlight, among other aspects, the presence of significant correlations between anthropometric parameters and cardiac resistance in junior athletes between the ages of 10 and 14. Acceleration of growth and development of children aged between 10-14 years, practicing sports games (soccer), may represent one of the causes of the decrease in cardiac resistance.*

Research limitations/implications: *Sport today has reached a high standard, so it is necessary to approach modern technologies, methods and objective models that will support the technicians and coaches in the world of sports. These models visualize the real potential of the athlete, the evolution of the individual's sports parameters, being able for the technician or coach to choose those exercises and trainings that develop the deficient elements, or to evaluate the performance or non-performance as such.*

Practical implications: *For a sports manager, he can make early decisions related to the potential of the subjects, if it is possible to increase cardiac endurance through education, physical culture and adequate and adapted training, or the subjects are possibly without sporting potential and thus everything comes down to a practicing sport for "pleasure", without speaking of performance.*

Originality/value: *It is generally accepted that a new approach is required, that the use of modern technologies is required in order to make sports management more efficient, to obtain real, objective results, and finally to increase sports performance.*

Key words: *Sports management, Sports performance, Sports potential, Anthropometric parameters, Modern technologies*

Introduction

It is generally accepted that a new approach is required, that the use of modern technologies is required in order to make sports management more efficient, to obtain real, objective results, and finally to increase sports performance. It is known that the COVID-19 Pandemic has affected the entire training and competition program of athletes. And from 2022, modern training technologies can once again be used to make the training of athletes more efficient, to increase the sports performance of the sports management, and to identify the real sports potential. The present paper proposes the structuring of this

scientific approach in five directions in order to streamline and maximize the modern methods of sports management, and in the present case study here only the first two directions of evaluation research will be used (the application of all 5 directions would lead to an exemption too size of the work). Specifically in this study we have: anthropometric evaluations and functional evaluations.

These parameters, height, weight, BMI and cardiac endurance among others, pencil in an indubitable way the possibilities and aptitudes of possible performance or possible non-performance of the subjects. Taking into account the diversity of sports specialties, the diversity of sports organizational entities as well as their functional types, this paper will focus on the basic constitutive element of the sports organization: namely the athlete, the athletes in order to make management methods more efficient. Depending on the types of sport practiced, we have group, intergroup and individual sports organizational entities. Group sports organizational entities existing in the case of team sports specialties: volleyball, handball, football, hockey, kayak canoe, etc., intergroup sports organizational entities being in the case of relay sports specialties, for example: athletics, swimming, gymnastics, etc., and the singular ones existing in the case of sports specialties such as: table tennis, field tennis.

Literature review. Equipment used for the study

- a. Anthropometric evaluations of the athlete, or the athletes constituting the organizational entities (has two sub-directions applied anthropometry: having as object anthropometric measurements: body lengths, diameter, perimeter, goniometry, dynamometry, body weight measurement, barometry - the center of gravity of the body, adipometry and qualitative anthropometry: segmental and body relations and proportions)
- b. Functional evaluations of the athlete, or the athletes constituting the organizational entities (directions of evaluation and research: applied physiology: evaluation of respiratory function, cardiac, muscular, vestibular function) [Blandine Calais, 2012]
- c. Motor evaluation (directions e evaluation and research: evaluation, monitoring and development of motor skills)
- d. Evaluation of human performance (research directions: evaluation, miniaturization and development of some factors of the performance capacity of athletes)
- e. Psychological and psychomotor evaluation (directions of research and evaluation: of the perceptive-cognitive-motor level in order to correct, perfect and develop new psycho-motor skills necessary for effective adaptation to an environment in continuous technological evolution, with a view to professional orientation) better orients the athlete in group entities: in football the athlete has better skills as a striker, defender, goalkeeper, etc.), practicing and training perceptive-cognitive-motor skills in order to convert them into skills (valid in all types of sports organizational entities: group, intergroup and singular).

Equipment and appliances used

- a. In anthropometric research [Nenciu, G., 2005]:
 - GPS 200 Postural Stability Analysis System (study the athlete in static balance),
 - Anthropometric frame of symmetry
 - Podoscope
 - Other devices-instruments: stopwatch, dynamometer, large and small goniometer, spirometer, measuring tapes of 5 and 10 m, caliper, tallimeter, compass diameter, metronome, electronic scale, simple 6 m ladder.
- b. In research and functional evaluation [Ionescu, A.; Caramoci, A., 2017]:
 - Aeroscan: allows the analysis of respiratory gases during physical exertion)
 - Minispir Light computerized spirometer that measures current or tidal volume (VT), expiratory reserve volume (ERV), inspiratory reserve volume (IRV), residual volume (RV), etc.
 - Pulse oximeter with Utech UT 100 sensor (provides instant, continuous and non-invasive measurement of hemoglobin oxygen saturation and heart rate)

- Zephyr performance systems: records and uses heart rate variability (HRV) as a tool to analyze the autonomic regulation system
- Treadmill H/P/COSMOS-MERCURY 4.0: movement capture facility and biomechanical analysis with multiple applications in: effort tests, creation of training programs, assessment of sports performance, medical recovery of the athlete-orthopedic, neurological.
- The Gyko Med S system: analyzes with great accuracy the deficit of musculoskeletal function
- Garmin Fenix 3 Bundle watch: it has 3 accelerometer-altimeter-barometer axes of high sensitivity with fast localization, helps athletes during leisure and high performances activities.
- BioFET: digital dynamometer - complex equipment that measures muscle strength and the frequency of muscle contractions

c. In motor research and evaluation [Victor, L., 2010].

- -OptoGait system (analysis of gait, dynamic balance and dynamic proprioceptive capacity
- - Witty Wireless training Timer equipment - evaluates reaction speed, reaction time, agility with the help of smart traffic lights and Witty timers

d. In research and evaluation of human performance [Neagu, N. 2012]; [Victor, L., 2010].

- Optojump device: optical analysis and measurement system that aims to develop specific and personalized programs for athletes, based exclusively on precise and objective information containing 41 test batteries aimed at measuring motor skills, speed with its forms of manifestation, muscular resistance, strength, power using as motor skills: walking, running and jumping
- Equipment HP COSMED T150 E LC med: it is a treadmill that allows the assessment of motor capacity without any risk, having an elevation of 0-25%, support bars for the hands, 28 stress test profiles.
- Garmin Fenix 5 multisport device: it is a watch intended for indoor or outdoor activities, which has functions for motorization of effort, functions regarding the location via GPS and Glonass satellite reception, functions for personalizing training programs and planning them (like exercise book)

e. In psychological and psychomotor research and evaluation [Hendrie, W. J.P. Pawliw-Fry, 2018]; [Neagu, N., 2012]; [Nunnally, J.C.; Bernstein, I.H. ,1994]:

- PSISELTEVA test batteries (alternative computerized system of sports psychological testing and evaluation in the field of athlete psychology and sports-professional orientation
- CAS++ evaluation platform
- Neuropsychological assessment battery for children aged 3-12 years (NEPSY)
- PED platform b

Methodology

The study was carried out in 2021 on a number of 124 subjects, male, aged between 10 and 14, members of some sports entities from Bucharest. Valid data were 34, as some respondents did not complete testing for all 16 anthropometric and functional parameters, or participation was derided by them. But for three parameters BMI, SPO2 and the Ruffier test all 124 respondents-athletes had valid data.

The individual evaluation was carried out within the Interdisciplinary Research Center of UNEFS in collaboration with the Sports Medicine Center - GRAL, after obtaining the consent of the parents and the informed consent of the evaluators-athletes. To obtain the necessary data, direct methods were used: anthropometric (height and weight) based on which the body mass index (BMI) and the O2 saturation in the arterial blood (SPO2) were calculated. Cardiac resistance was assessed using the Ruffier (IR) test.

This index provides exactly the necessary parameters, that is: knowledge of the tonic state of the myocardium before exercise (at rest), the ability of the myocardium to adapt to exercise, and the power

to return to normal after exercise. For this purpose, a standard exercise was used, consisting of 30 squats (according to the J.E. Ruffier method). The Ruffier index was calculated according to the formula: $IC = P1 + P2 + P3 - 200/10$ (where P1= the number of pulses per minute at rest, P2 = the number of pulses per minute after exertion, in the first 10 seconds, P3 = the number of pulses per minute 3 minutes after exercise). The data collection was carried out with the help of the portable medical device - Oxi-Capnograph (Pulse Oximeter) MD-660P; device to which different peripherals can be connected to measure some parameters (SpO2, FC, CO2 from exhaled air, FR) This is a non-invasive method that provides precise results that can be processed in real time with the help of the Smart Link V software application; application that converts data saved in physical curve information Through an easy-to-use interface, the user can store and long-term follow-up information on the dynamics of the tested parameters.

The statistical processing of the data was carried out with the help of mathematical models and Pearson correlation coefficients. To mathematically model, visualize, process the experimental data and to determine the law of mathematical variation of BMI (body mass index), IR (Ruffier cardiac resistance index), SpO2 (oxygen saturation present in hemoglobin), am used variational mathematical calculation, using some methods of determining the laws of variation of these indicators (variables) with the help of 4 types of mathematical regressions: polynomial regression, logarithmic regression, linear regression and exponential regression [Chatelin, F., 2012].

The determination method consists in creating, within the Microsoft Office Excel software, a functional matrix of the $\mathbb{R}(m,1)$ type, i.e. m lines and 1 column, in our case 124 lines and 1 column $\mathbb{R}(124,1)$, where the figure of 124 represents the number of subjects with valid data and with the help of some functions in this program, XY Scatter for example, let's represent the graph, the law of variation related to the type of regression as well as the confidence coefficient R. The confidence coefficient R shows us the fidelity of both of the determined variation law, as well as the objectivity of the method of determining and representing the variation law of the studied parameters.

Results

For a sports manager, he can make early decisions related to the potential of the subjects, if it is possible to increase cardiac endurance through education, physical culture and adequate and adapted training, or the subjects are possibly without sporting potential and thus everything comes down to a practicing sport for "pleasure", without speaking of performance.

For the BMI body mass index, the graphic representation in the order of determining the valid experimental data resulted in figure 1 and figure 2. The performance of the determination of these measurements did not have a selection of the subjects, they were measured in random order. For visualization, mathematical modeling and graphic representation in order to determine the trend of BMI increase or decrease, or invariance, in the sample presented above, methods were used4 of mathematical regressions.

Figure 1. The law of variation of the body mass index MBI. Polynomial regression of order 6

From the processing in fig.1 we notice a very low index $r=0.1462$, a fact that does not indicate that the measured organisms are growing, in continuous anthropometric change, we do not have stable organisms, with completed anthropometric development. horizontal, which does not indicate that this sample of subjects does not have a significant differentiation of the body mass parameter, i.e. by extension the current generation of subjects does not differ from the generations before the Covid Pandemic. The graph was obtained with the help of the Trendline package by choosing the type of polynomial regression of order 2, from the Scatter functions in Excel. Data obtained from measurements were placed vertically and using the functions above, the graph was obtained, with the equation of the law of variation and the representation of the dispersion cloud in question.

Analogously, applying in the same way as for the graph in fig.1, where this time we applied another type of linear regression, we obtain in fig.2, another but similar graph, a horizontal-"stationary" graph, which it also indicates that in this generation there is no significant change in the BMI parameter, due to the Covid Pandemic or the different evolution compared to previous generations.

Figure 2. The law of variation of the body mass index BMI linear regression

We apply for the Ruffier cardiac resistance index (IR) in the same way the same Trendline package with different types of regressions, applying the XY Scatter functions and obtain the graphs in fig.3 and fig.4. with the laws of variation superimposed on them.

By applying the 2nd order polynomial regression as shown in fig.3 we notice this law of variation, it is coarse, it has a negative r index. This can be explained in 2 ways: either the regression is not suitable for the description of the IR variation, or the subjects do not have the adequate physical preparation and warm-up to start the measurements.

Figure 3. The law of variation of the Ruffier IR cardiac resistance index of the 2nd order polynomial regression type

For the experimental data in fig.4, after graphical visualization, we notice a "stationary" graph similar to a horizontal one. The law of exponential regression would reduce to a form of linear regression. And here the same thing is noted as in the BMI study, that it is a state of invariance. Biometrically speaking, it would have been unnatural to have such large jumps in the BMI and IR indices of the current generation compared to previous generations, or due to the COVID Pandemic.

Figure 4. The law of variation of the Ruffier IR cardiac resistance index of logarithmic regression type

Conclusions

The present work by extension for all five directions of evaluation research allows the efficiency of modern management through the use of advanced equipment and devices:

- for the research-anthropometric evaluation, the sports manager has the undoubted possibility to decide, related to the athletes, their potential, and if it is insufficient where the sports activities must be improved, or if for the real performance that approach is worthwhile, or the athlete is limited to a practice without performance.
- for the research-functional evaluation, the same way the manager through these advanced techniques makes his management more efficient, he also knows what exactly he has to do to increase the sports performance, the direction of application of the physical training. All these researches indicate to the manager whether it makes sense to undertake effective training for that subject or not. These parameters objectively tell us the functionality of the athlete in question.
- for motor evaluation and research, this work allows, by using the same mathematical models, to establish the evolution or non-evolution of speed, reaction times, which in certain sports specialties (martial arts, football, handball, basketball, tennis, etc.) are overwhelmingly important elements
- the direction of human performance evaluation, in an analogous way to the above, allows the efficiency of the modern management act, using the interdisciplinary technologies presented in the devices and equipment section of this work
- the direction of psychological research-evaluation and psychomotricity also allows for the improvement and making of managerial decisions related to athletes. Managers analyzing with the help of advanced evaluation tools: analytical reasoning, working memory, cognitive inhibition, attention switching, decision-making capacity, organizational capacity (especially in group specialties: football, rugby, etc.) of athletes.

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